

The Impact of AI Tools on Project Communication in Sri Lankan Software Projects: A Qualitative Study

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools on project communication within software development environments. With communication recognized as a critical success factor in software projects, the research explores how AI tools enhance, modify, or challenge traditional communication processes. This study is theoretically grounded in Adaptive Structuration Theory, Media Richness Theory, Social Penetration Theory, and AI Governance Frameworks to explore the impact of AI tools on project communication in software projects. A qualitative research methodology was employed, involving eight semi-structured interviews with professionals from Sri Lankan software companies. The data were transcribed using the Riverside AI tool, reviewed for accuracy, and analyzed through thematic analysis using Braun and Clarke's framework. QDA Miner Lite was used for systematic coding. Six key themes emerged: Efficiency and Timesaving; Enhanced Clarity and Standardization; Tool Limitations and Dependency Risks; Privacy, Ethics, and Governance; Bridging Cross-Functional Roles; and Adoption Barriers and Cultural Resistance. AI tools improved communication speed and accessibility, but also raised concerns about data security, overreliance, and contextual misinterpretation. The findings contribute to academic discourse by emphasizing communication, not just automation, as a central domain of AI impact in project environments. They also introduce a conceptual map that illustrates the relationship between AI tools, 6 themes, and project communication outcomes in software projects. The findings provide practical guidance for software organizations and project managers on responsibly selecting, governing, and contextualizing AI communication tools to improve coordination, inclusivity, and adoption. The study's qualitative scope limits generalizability. Future research could expand with mixed method approaches or explore AI's communication impact in cross-cultural or multilingual teams.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Software projects, Software development, Project communication; Thematic analysis*